

Synthesis of Zn₂SnO₄ particles and the influence of annealing temperature on the structural and optical properties of Zn₂SnO₄ films deposited by spraying nanoinks

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the results of the study of structural, substructural and optical properties of Zn₂SnO₄ nanoparticles (NPs) and films. NPs synthesized by the hydrothermal method during 28 h were chosen to form a nanoink from which films were obtained by spraying the solution it on glass substrates. Obtained Zn₂SnO₄ films were annealed in Argon atmosphere at $T_a = (250-500)^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min and 60 min to remove organic impurities and optimize the film's physical properties. Since the choice of mineralizer determines a number of important characteristics of nanoparticles, a comprehensive study of the obtained samples grown using KOH as a mineralizer was conducted. The samples were characterized by X-ray diffraction analysis, Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis, high-resolution transmission (HRTEM) and scanning electron (SEM) microscopy, Raman and optical spectroscopy. Analysis of morphology showed that synthesized films have a [220] growth texture with inverse spinel structure and consist of NPs, the size of which increases with the annealing temperature (T_a). It was identified that the size of the coherent scattering domain (CSD) in the sample increases with increasing T_a , while the level of microdeformations decreases. Raman spectra showed $F_{2g}(2)$, $F_{2g}(3)$ and A_{1g} modes corresponding to the structure of inverse spinel Zn₂SnO₄. It is found, that the optical bandgap E_g of NPs decreases from 4.02 eV to 3.85 eV with an increase in growth time. On another hand, the optical bandgap E_g of films decreases with an increase in annealing temperature, T_a , from 4.04 eV to 3.63 eV.

Introduction

Multicomponent oxide compounds in the form of nanoparticles (NP) and films have immense potential for application in electronics, catalysis, and solar engineering [1,2]. This capability might be explained by the appearance of new properties in multicomponent oxides in comparison with well-studied binary systems [3,4]. Oxide materials are well-known for their good electrical and optical properties and multicomponent oxide materials possess, in addition, more freedom in control of such properties by changing the chemical composition [5,6]. Binary compounds like tin oxide (SnO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO) are chemically stable, environmentally safe and consist of widely distributed elements in Earth's crust [7,8]. Moreover, a great interest is also devoted to SnO₂-ZnO based alloy system, where two crystallographic phases as orthorhombic ZnSnO₃ (metastannate) and cubic with an inverted spinel

structure Zn₂SnO₄ (orthostannate) are usually present. At the same time, zinc metastannate is metastable and turns into orthostannate at a temperature close to 500 °C. Due to its stability in a wide temperature range the spinel structure is more effective for applications in electronics [9, 10].

Zinc orthostannate (ZTO) is known as an important multifunctional material with a wide band gap ($E_g = (3.4-4.2)$ eV), high electron mobility ($\mu = (10-15)$ cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹), low absorption coefficient in the visible optical spectrum and controlled structure of electronic bands [11]. These unique properties led to the wide application of the compound for the development of photovoltaic converters [12,13], anodes of lithium-ion batteries [14], catalysts and photocatalyst [15], transparent conductive layers [16], combustible gas and moisture sensors [17,18].

Zn₂SnO₄ NPs and films have been obtained by various methods

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including thermal evaporation [19], chemical vapor deposition [20], spray pyrolysis [21], sol-gel [22] co-precipitation [23], hydrothermal [14] and electrospinning [18] methods. The hydrothermal method is considered one of the effective NPs synthesis approaches [14,24,25] at low growth temperatures by applying different mineralization agents, including NaOH [24,26–28], Na_2CO_3 [25,29], butylamine [25,27,30]. Nevertheless, KOH is rarely used for the synthesis of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs [25, 31]. However, the authors [31] established that the mineralizer affects a number of important characteristics of NPs, such as their size, shape, specific surface area, etc. Thus, changing the mineralizer could allow to synthesis of particles with the desired characteristics.

Nowadays, there is an increasing interest in growing films of semiconductor materials by non-vacuum chemical methods. This is due to the fact that the chemical approach can be more energy efficient, cheap and adapted to large-scale industrial production [32,33]. This approach allows to grow films of large area on various types of substrates, including flexible ones. However, usually, the obtained films by some chemical methods require annealing to remove organic impurities and optimize characteristics [25].

An effective strategy for obtaining films of multicomponent semiconductors with a controlled crystal structure requires a process in which the chemical colloidal synthesis of NPs is followed by the deposition of their suspension (nanoink) on substrates using non-vacuum methods, and, finally, post-growth thermal annealing of the obtained samples [25]. This approach was tested by us on a number of oxide and multicomponent compounds, such as ZnO, CuO, and CZTSSe [34–36]. It was well established that the structural and substructural characteristics of thin layers, their phase composition, lattice parameters, and the sizes of coherent scattering domains (CSD) depend on the conditions of preparation of NPs and films and post-growth annealing. In spite of the possibilities of the above-described process, layers obtained by sputtering nano-inks remain poorly studied. Only some oxide films obtained by this method have been somewhat studied [7,21,37,38].

In this work, we synthesized Zn_2SnO_4 NPs using the hydrothermal method, from these NPs and we grew films on glass substrates by sputtering nanoinks with a printer injector. Further, the films were

annealed in an argon environment to remove organic impurities and stabilize structural, microstructural and optical characteristics, which have been analyzed.

Experimental

Preparation of materials

Zn_2SnO_4 NPs were synthesized by the hydrothermal method. Zn $(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ taken in stoichiometric quantities 2:1 were mixed in deionized water. Then, KOH alkali solution was slowly added as a mineralizer. The resulting solution was placed in a steel autoclave with teflon insert and heated to 200 °C. The growth time varied in the range from 16 h to 32 h with $\Delta t_g = 4$ h. Then, the nanoparticles synthesized during 28 h were re-dispersed in distilled water to form a nanoink solution. Subsequently, the nanoinks were sprayed onto glass substrates, resulting in Zn_2SnO_4 film formation. The basic flow chart of the setup for spraying nanoinks and synthesis of films described in the experimental part is presented in Fig. 1.

Such films were annealed in Argon environment at (250–500 °C) with $\Delta T_a = 50$ °C for 30 min. Sample annealed at 400 °C was also annealed for 60 min.

Characterization methods

The structural and morphological properties of Zn_2SnO_4 films were studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Hitachi S-4800) equipped with a Bruker X-ray detector for energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX). The working voltage during the measurements was 20 kV, the current was 10 mA. Magnification was chosen $\times 100$ K to study the surface morphology and $\times 3$ K to determine the thickness in cross sectional measurements.

A more detailed microstructural analysis (including SAED and FFT patterns) was carried out by a high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) Tecnai G2 F20 with an emission gun under an accelerating voltage of 200 kV.

Fig. 1. Diagram of the experimental setup for Zn_2SnO_4 films growth.

Structural and phase analysis was carried out with Bruker D8 Advance A25 diffractometers in Ni-filtered K_{α} copper anode radiation in the range of 2θ diffraction angles from 20° to 90° . X-ray focusing was carried out in the Bragg-Brentano geometry. The phase analysis was carried out by comparing the interplanar distances, as well as the relative intensity of the diffraction lines of the samples and reference data from the compounds Zn_2SnO_4 (JCPDS card No. 024–1470), $ZnSnO_3$ (JCPDS card No. 011–0274), $Zn_2Sn(OH)_6$ (JCPDS card No. 020–1455), SnO_2 (JCPDS card No. 041–1445), ZnO (JCPDS card No. 036–1451). The texture of the films was evaluated according to the Harris method [39].

The calculation of the lattice constant a of the cubic phase of zinc orthostannate was carried out by using all the lines present in the diffractograms by the following formula:

$$a = \frac{\lambda}{2\sin\theta} \sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2}, \quad (1)$$

where λ —wavelength of X-ray radiation; θ —the Bragg angle; h, k, l —Miller indices.

Afterwards, the Nelson-Riley extrapolation method was used to obtain precise values of the lattice constants [40]. Linear approximation of the $a - 1/2 \cos^2\theta(1/\sin(\theta)+1/\theta)$ relation was carried out using the least squares method. The volume of the unit cell of the compound was calculated according to the equation: $V_{unit} = a^3$.

XRD method was also used to determine the average size of coherent scattering domains (CSD, L) and the level of microstrains ε in zinc orthostannate samples by using physical broadening β of the diffraction peaks (220), (311), (440) using the Debye-Scherrer and Stoke-Wilson ratios:

$$L = 0.94 \frac{\lambda}{\beta \cdot \cos(\theta)}, \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon = \beta \cdot \cos(\theta) / 4 \quad (3)$$

where β — full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the diffraction peak.

Since the crystallographic (220), (440) planes are parallel, the Williamson-Hall method was also used to determine the substructural parameters of the samples. This made possible to separate the contributions to the physical broadening of the diffraction lines from the dispersion of the CSD, β_L and microdeformations β_e . To separate the diffraction broadening caused by physical (β_p) and instrumental (β_i) effects, approximations of the X-ray line profile by Cauchy and Gaussian functions were used. Algorithms to determine structural and substructural characteristics of semiconductor materials were described in more detail in our previous works [36,41,42].

The crystal quality of annealed Zn_2SnO_4 samples was carried out at room temperature using the Raman spectroscopy (Horiba MTB XPlora) in the frequency range of (200–1000) cm^{-1} with a 532 nm laser having an intensity of 0.78 mW. Raman study was carried out with three times accumulation signal during 30 s each. An Olympus BX 41 microscope with $100 \times$ magnification and a diffraction grating of 1200 lines per mm^{-1} was used.

The optical characteristics of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs and films were measured using a Cary 4000 spectrophotometer (Varian) in the wavelength range $\lambda = (200–900)$ nm at room temperatures. The spectral dependences of the light transmission coefficient $T(\lambda)$ of the samples were recorded. Absorption spectra were determined by transmission spectra using the Lambert's law [43]. To determine the optical band gap (E_g), the following ratio for direct bandgap materials was used [44]:

$$\alpha_i h\nu = A_0 (h\nu - E_g)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (4)$$

where A_0 is the constant that depends on the effective mass of charge carriers; $h\nu$ is the energy of optical quanta. The extrapolation of the linear part of the graph $(\alpha h\nu)^2 - h\nu$ onto the energy axis allows to determine E_g of the semiconductor material.

Results and discussion

TEM images of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs synthesized from 20 h to 32 h are shown in Fig. 2. Micrographs show both individual particles and their agglomerates. It was established that with an increase in growth time, the size of NPs increased from $D = (20–36)$ nm ($t_g = 20$ h) to $D = (22–49)$ nm ($t_g = 32$ h). At the same time, some particles possess a cubic shape and others have an irregular shape. Such results correlate well with the data of the work [25] where synthesized NPs with sizes of (15–35) nm were obtained by hydrothermal method.

XRD patterns of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs synthesized at different times are shown in Fig. 3a. The insets present reference data on the position of the diffraction lines for compounds Zn_2SnO_4 , $ZnSnO_3$, $Zn_2Sn(OH)_6$, SnO_2 , ZnO . As can be seen from the figure, peaks correspond to reflections from (220), (311), (400), (422), (511), (440), (533) crystallographic planes of Zn_2SnO_4 compound with a cubic inverse spinel structure (JCPDS No. 00–024–1470). At the same time, the diffraction line corresponding to the reflection from (311) plane dominates on all diffractograms.

The diffractogram from the sample obtained during a growth time of 16 h indicates its multiphase composition. It consists of a cubic phase of Zn_2SnO_4 and an intermediate phase of $ZnSn(OH)_6$ which indicates an incomplete reaction during hydrothermal synthesis. At the same time, XRD patterns of NPs synthesized for 20 h, 24 h, 28 h and 32 h show their single-phase composition which corresponds to zinc orthostannate. Such samples, within the accuracy of the method, do not contain crystalline secondary impurity phases, such as $ZnSn(OH)_6$, $ZnSnO_3$, SnO_2 and ZnO .

We used the results of XRD studies to determine the parameters of the cubic lattice of NPs. It is known that the spatial period of the crystal lattice of a material is a characteristic that is extremely sensitive to changes in its stoichiometry, the introduction of impurities, microdeformations, that is why precise measurement of such parameters makes it possible to study relevant processes. The calculation of the a lattice parameter was carried out using the Nelson-Riley approximation method [40]. The corresponding results are shown in Table 1.

As can be seen from the table, the value of the lattice period of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs calculated by Eq. (1) varied in the interval of $a = (0.86433–0.86676)$ nm. It was found that as the growth time increases, the lattice parameter of the NPs decreases slightly, stabilizing at time $t_g = (20–24)$ h and then increases. The obtained values are quite close to those given in the reference data (JCPDS card No. 024–1470) for zinc orthostannate ($a = 0.86574$ nm), which confirms the synthesis of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs. Somewhat larger values of $a = (0.8701–0.8869)$ nm were obtained by the authors [31] based on the position of various peaks on the XRD patterns of NPs synthesized by hydrothermal method using, as in our case, KOH as a mineralizer.

EDX spectra from Zn_2SnO_4 films are shown in Fig. 4. As can be seen from the figure, the spectra reveal only the lines of the main components of the compound, and in the case of films, silicon is also present which comes from the sample holder. In the films annealed at low temperatures, carbon was also detected, which could get into the films from the precursors. The processing of the spectra made possible to find the atomic concentrations of the constituent elements of zinc stannate. Based on these results, their ratio was subsequently found, which determines the stoichiometry of the compound.

The obtained results are summarized in Table 2, the ratio of element concentrations (C_i/C_j) is also given there. It was found that as the synthesis time increases, the concentration of oxygen in NPs first decreases, and then begins to increase. At the same time, an opposite trend was observed for the atomic concentration of Zn and Sn. The chemical composition closest to the stoichiometric had particles synthesized during $t_g = 28$ h ($C_{Zn} = 28.20$, $C_{Sn} = 14.00$, $C_O = 57.79$). The ratio of the concentrations of the constituent elements ($C_{Zn}/C_{Sn} = 2.01$, $C_{Zn}/C_O = 0.49$, $C_{Sn}/C_O = 0.24$) was obtained close to the stoichiometric material ($C_{Zn}/C_{Sn} = 2.00$, $C_{Zn}/C_O = 0.50$, $C_{Sn}/C_O = 0.25$). However, they were somewhat depleted in zinc and tin but enriched in oxygen. When the

Fig. 2. TEM micrographs of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs synthesized at different growth times, t_g , h: 20 (a); 24 (b); 28 (c) and 32 (d). The inset part is the diffraction pattern from NPs.

synthesis time is increased to 32 h, the composition of NPs becomes intermediate between Zn_2SnO_4 and ZnSnO_3 phases. The oxide films contained an excess of tin and less oxygen compared to the stoichiometric compound. As the annealing temperature increased, the concentration of tin and zinc in the layers decreased, and oxygen increased. The possibility of the presence of elements or compounds with an amorphous structure in the sample cannot be excluded.

TEM images of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs synthesized for 32 h are shown in Fig. 5. Analysis of the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern showed the presence of crystallographic planes of ZTO with a cubic type of structure, which coincides with the data obtained by XRD method. It is worth mentioning that the reflection from (111) plane observed in Fig. 5c was not recorded by the XRD technique, since the reflection from (111) plane occurs at angles $2\theta = 17.72^\circ$, which were not included in the range of our study, and therefore were not recorded experimentally by the XRD method. Using Fast-Fourier-transform, it was calculated that the interplanar distance for reflection from the (311) plane of the material is $d_{(311)} = 0.2656$ nm, which is slightly larger than the reference data for orthostannate $d_{(311)} = 0.2613$ nm. In addition, HRTEM-EDX analysis of the oxide was carried out.

Measurements were made at three different points and next the average value was taken. This analysis showed that the atomic ratio of zinc and tin concentrations was approximately $C_{\text{Zn}/\text{Sn}} \sim 1$, which is inconsistent with the value of $C_{\text{Zn}/\text{Sn}} = 2$ for Zn_2SnO_4 compound. This indicates that the content of such NPs may contain inclusions of

amorphous material, like ZnSnO_3 phase or tin agglomerates. It is worth to note that the diffraction patterns of SAED and FFT do not have signs of the presence of the ZnSnO_3 phase in the nanoparticles and/or tin oxide phases. It should be noted that the interplanar distance from the plane (104) of ZnSnO_3 with the higher intensity is $d_{(104)} = 0.2791$ at $2\theta = 32.0^\circ$ (JCPDS card No. 01-089-0095), which is significantly larger than the value calculated by us from FFT patterns. On the other hand, the interplanar distance from the second most intense plane (110) is $d_{(110)} = 0.2642$ nm, which is much closer to the value we obtained. It is interesting that the position of this reflection $2\theta = 33.91^\circ$ (ZnSnO_3 [110]) is quite close to the position of the reflection (311) of the Zn_2SnO_4 compound at $2\theta = 34.29^\circ$, so it could be assumed that they could be overlapped, which leads to an increase in the FWHM of the peak. However, the reflection from other planes of the ZnSnO_3 compound using the XRD method in Fig. 3b was not found. Moreover, Fig. 5c shows a clear orientation of planes characteristic of Zn_2SnO_4 . Then it seems that if the ZnSnO_3 inclusions or tin agglomerates should be, if present, non-crystalline.

Thus, among all the Zn_2SnO_4 NPs series obtained during different growth times, NPs synthesized for 28 h had the best characteristics and a chemical composition close to the Zn_2SnO_4 compound, which is why they were used later to create nanoinks for spraying zinc orthostannate films.

Surface micrographs of Zn_2SnO_4 films are shown in Fig. 6. As can be seen from the figure, these films consist of grains whose size is $D =$

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of Zn₂SnO₄ NPs synthesized at (16–32) h (a), films annealed at $T_a = (250–500)^\circ\text{C}$ (b).

Table 1

Structural and substructural characteristics of Zn₂SnO₄ NPs and films.

t_g , h	T_a , °C	a_{H-P} , nm	V_{unit} , nm ³	L , nm				$\varepsilon \cdot 10^3$					E_g , eV	
				(220)	(311)	(440)	Cauchy	Gauss	(220)	(311)	(440)	Cauchy		Gauss
NPs														
16		0.86635	0.65025	10.4	8.9	9.2	13.6	9.8	3.5	4.1	3.9	2.7	11.2	4.02
20		0.86441	0.64589	7.7	7.4	8.5	9.4	8.7	4.7	4.9	4.3	1.8	5.2	3.97
24		0.86433	0.64571	8.4	7.8	8.9	10.1	9.2	4.3	4.7	4.1	1.8	4.9	3.94
28		0.86441	0.64589	8.2	8.4	9.2	12.3	10.7	4.4	4.3	3.9	2.8	6.1	3.91
32		0.86676	0.65117	10.3	6.9	8.8	12.1	9.6	3.5	5.2	4.1	3.4	6.2	2.56, 3.85
Films														
250 (30)		0.86538	0.64807	6.0	16.7	17.5	3.9	5.6	6.0	2.2	2.1	15.8	13.1	4.04
300 (30)		0.86629	0.65011	5.0	15.0	14.2	3.2	4.7	7.2	2.4	2.5	18.7	15.6	3.93
350 (30)		0.86704	0.6518	5.4	12.4	14.8	3.4	5.0	6.8	2.9	2.4	18.8	14.8	3.85
400 (30)		0.86825	0.65454	5.5	12.9	18.3	3.5	5.1	6.5	2.8	2.0	18.2	14.4	3.75
400 (60)		0.86901	0.65626	13.0	14.2	15.7	11.8	13.0	2.8	2.5	2.3	1.9	3.4	3.78
450 (30)		0.86890	0.65601	6.4	10.9	17.4	4.3	6.1	5.5	3.3	2.1	13.8	11.9	3.63
500 (30)		0.86827	0.65458	8.3	11.8	13.3	6.4	8.0	4.4	3.1	2.7	6.5	7.8	3.76
JCPDS			$a = 0.86574$ nm, $V_{unit} = 0.64888$ nm ³											

(28–36)±6 nm depending on the annealing temperature (T_a), which is close to the values obtained in [45]. As expected, the higher annealing temperature of the films led to the recrystallization of the grains, which increased their size. Calculations were performed for each film at the maximum cluster of 100+ grains. Exceptionally, for the film annealed at an average temperature of $T_a = 350^\circ\text{C}$, the value of D varied in the range from 16.2 nm to 69.0 nm. The thickness of the films was $d = (4.90–8.45)$ μm.

XRD patterns of Zn₂SnO₄ films annealed at the different temperatures are presented in Fig. 3b. Significantly fewer peaks were recorded

with respect to the corresponding X-ray patterns from NPs, while the intensity remains dominated by the reflection from (311) plane. The analysis of the diffractograms shows that all the observed reflections correspond to Zn₂SnO₄ compound with the inverse cubic spinel structure. Thus, the obtained films are single-phase and no secondary crystalline phases were recorded by the XRD method.

For a very accurate study, TEM images with SAED patterns were analyzed to validate the XRD results. For this purpose, the film material was separated from the substrates and ground. It can be seen from Fig. 7 that for all the samples the diffraction rings correspond to the reflection

Fig. 4. SEM-EDX mapping of chemical elements of Zn_2SnO_4 films annealed at different temperatures (T_a , °C) for 30 min: 250 (a); 300 (b); 350 (c); 400 (d); 450 (e) and 500 (f). Zn+Sn+O are each element separately.

from the (311), (400) and (440) planes of the Zn_2SnO_4 spinel structure. No reflections were found corresponding to other crystalline phases. Studies showed that with an increase in the annealing temperature in the range of (250–500) °C, the grain size increases from 22 nm to 39 nm, respectively.

Calculations of the pole density $P_{(hkl)}$ using the method of inverted pole figures made possible to reveal the [220] growth texture in Zn_2SnO_4 films (Fig. 8). Corresponding calculations were carried out for films annealed above a temperature of 350 °C, where a sufficiently large number of diffraction lines was recorded on the diffractograms. Further calculation of the orientation factor made possible to determine the effect of annealing on the quality of the texture. It was established that the texture quality of the films improves when the annealing temperature is increased to $T_a = 450$ °C. A further increase in temperature, however,

led to a decrease in the quality of the texture of films, as well as an increase in the annealing time from 30 to 60 min.

The results presented in Table 1 which shows that the lattice parameter of the annealed zinc orthostannate films was higher ($a = 0.86538\text{--}0.86901$ nm) than that of NPs used to create ink ($a = 0.86441$ nm). This lattice parameter increases monotonically as the annealing temperature increases from 250 °C to 450 °C, and then decreases slightly. All calculated values of a , except that for the film annealed at 250 °C ($a = 0.86538$ nm) were higher than those of the stoichiometric compound given in the reference ($a = 0.86574$ nm). An increase in the annealing time from 30 to 60 min leads to an increase in the lattice parameter of the material from $a = 0.86825$ nm to $a = 0.86901$ nm. It should be noted that the graph of the $a - T_a$ dependence constructed from the values of the lattice parameter determined by the

Table 2
Chemical composition of Zn₂SnO₄ NPs and films.

t_s, h	$C_{Zn}, at. \%$	$C_{Sn}, at. \%$	$C_O, at. \%$	C_{Zn}/C_{Sn}	C_O/C_{Zn}	C_O/C_{Sn}	
NPs							
16	18.21	9.78	72.01	1.86	3.95	7.36	
20	30.30	13.91	55.79	2.18	1.84	4.01	
24	29.88	14.07	56.05	2.12	1.88	3.98	
28	28.20	14.00	57.79	2.01	2.05	4.13	
32	22.20	13.28	64.52	1.67	2.91	4.86	
Films							
250 (30)	29.51	20.03	50.45	1.47	1.71	2.51	
300 (30)	29.03	19.48	51.47	1.49	1.77	2.64	
350 (30)	28.79	19.35	51.85	1.49	1.80	2.68	
400 (30)	25.54	17.79	56.74	1.44	2.22	3.19	
450 (30)	26.27	17.58	56.14	1.49	2.02	3.02	
500 (30)	27.12	18.49	54.30	1.47	2.00	2.24	
Reference	Zn ₂ SnO ₄	28.57	14.29	57.14	2.00	2.00	4.00
	ZnSnO ₃	20.00	20.00	60.00	1.00	3.00	3.00

Nelson-Riley method was similar to that constructed from the values of a found from the positions of the reflections from (311) and (440) crystallographic planes.

We also determined the volume of the unit cell of zinc orthostannate (Table 1). It turned out that for NPs it varies from $V_{unit} = 0.64571 \text{ nm}^3$ to 0.65117 nm^3 , while for films it extends on a wider range $V_{unit} = (0.64807\text{--}0.65626) \text{ nm}^3$. The trends of the unit cell volume change with a change in the annealing temperature follow to those of the $a - T_a$ dependence, i.e., it monotonically increased when T_s changed from 250 °C to 450 °C, and then slightly decreased.

The obtained values agree well with the results given in [46] for films applied by the spray pyrolysis method at a temperature of 400 °C and then annealed in Argon at a temperature of $T_a = 600 \text{ °C}$ and 800 °C for 1

h ($a = (0.86165\text{--}0.86640) \text{ nm}$, $V_{unit} = (0.63973\text{--}0.65037) \text{ nm}^3$).

The peculiarities of the substructure of Zn₂SnO₄ films have been rarely studied [47,48], but they can significantly affect the functional characteristics of devices created based on such thin layers. It is known that dislocations, which form small-angle boundaries CSD and lead to the occurrence of microdeformation in NPs and films, can act as traps or deep recombination centers for charge carriers, determining the electrophysical characteristics of the material, in particular, the lifetime of charge carriers [48]. This determines the relevance of the study of the substructural characteristics of NPs and zinc stannate films depending on the conditions of their annealing, and the need for their optimization, i.e. the selection of technological parameters under which the concentration of these defects is reduced.

To determine the size of the CSD and the level of microdeformations in the samples X-ray analysis was used. It is known that, in addition to instrumental effects, the physical broadening of X-ray lines is contributed by the small size of the CSD (L), the presence of microdeformations ($\epsilon = \Delta d/d$) and structural imperfections of the crystal lattice, such as packing defects [49]. Usually, in most studies [50,51], it is considered that the physical broadening of the diffraction peaks either is caused only by the dispersion of the CSD or by the presence of microdeformations, then the Debye-Scherrer and Stoke-Wilson ratios (2)-(3) are used to determine L and ϵ . To separate these effects, the Williamson-Hall approximation method is usually used for X-ray peaks approximated by Cauchy and Gaussian functions, depending on their shape [52]. We used both of these methods to determine the substructural characteristics of zinc stannate NPs and films. Reflections from parallel crystallographic planes (220) and (440) were used to separate the contributions of L and ϵ .

To determine the average size of the CSD, the calculation of L was also carried out based on reflections from (220), (311) and (440) crystallographic planes. In the following, we will mainly discuss the results

Fig. 5. TEM images of Zn₂SnO₄ NPs synthesized for 32 h. SAED pattern (a) with reflections from different planes; HRTEM image for individual nanocrystals (b), and FFT pattern (c) for determining the interplanar distances are given.

Fig. 6. SEM images of Zn_2SnO_4 films annealed for 30 min at the different temperatures, T_a , °C: 250 (a), 350 (b), 400 (c) and 500 (d).

obtained by the Williamson-Hall approximation method. It was established (Table 1) that with increasing growth time, the size of the CSD of NPs in the direction perpendicular to (220) plane initially decreased, but starting from $t_g = 20$ h, that is, in single-phase samples, it began to increase. The maximum size (both using the approximation of the shape of the lines by Cauchy and Gaussian functions) in the CSD of particles was obtained for a growth time of 28 h (12.1 nm – Cauchy, 9.6 nm – Gaussian). A further increase in t_g led to a slight decrease in the size of the CSD, L (12.3 nm – Cauchy, 10.7 nm – Gaussian). A comparison of these results with the data of SEM ($D = (29.0\text{--}35.5)$ nm) shows that the synthesized NPs apparently consisted of several CSDs. At the same time, an increase in the growth time led to a slight increase in the level of microdeformation in the samples obtained at $t_g > 20$ h. Other authors [31], synthesized NPs by the method of hydrothermal synthesis using KOH as a mineralizer, according to the half-width of the reflection from the crystallographic (311) plane using the Debye-Scherrer relationship, they obtained a slightly larger value of $L = 25.2$ nm. However, this value does not consider the presence of microdeformations in the films and it is overestimated.

In Zn_2SnO_4 films, with increased annealing temperature, the size of the CSD increases from $L = 3.9$ nm (Cauchy) – 5.6 nm (Gauss) at $T_a = 250$ °C to $L \sim 6.4$ nm – 8.0 nm at $T_a = 500$ °C, and the level of microdeformations calculated by Eq. (3) decreases from $\varepsilon = (15.8\text{--}13.1) \cdot 10^{-3}$ (250 °C) to $\varepsilon = (6.5\text{--}7.8) \cdot 10^{-3}$ (500 °C). A particularly sharp increase in the size of the CSD $L = (11.8\text{--}13.0)$ nm and a decrease in the level of microdeformations was observed in the film annealed for 60 min: $\varepsilon = (1.9\text{--}3.4) \cdot 10^{-3}$ (400 °C). Then increasing the annealing time proved to be more effective, even increasing the annealing temperature to 500 °C (30 min) – $\varepsilon = (6.5\text{--}7.8) \cdot 10^{-3}$.

The size of the CSD in NPs used to create ink ($L = (12.3\text{--}10.7)$ nm) turned out to be slightly larger than in films ($L = (3.9\text{--}5.6)$ nm (250 °C)), perhaps due to the peculiarities of creating suspensions for printing thin

layers (centrifuging NPs and applying ultrasound to disperse them). At the same time, the level of microdeformations in thin layers was 4.8–6.6 (Cauchy), and 1.9–2.5 (Gaussian) times higher than in NPs. The exception was the samples annealed at 60 min and at $T_a = 500$ °C, where it was commensurate with the values found in NPs.

Joined to XRD studies, we used the Raman method to determine the phase composition and crystalline quality of Zn_2SnO_4 films. The recording of the corresponding spectra of the films was carried out at room temperature in the range of wavenumbers (50–1000) cm^{-1} . The corresponding dependencies are presented in Fig. 9a. As can be seen, a number of peaks of vibrational modes on the spectra are overlapped. Fig. 9b shows an example of the decomposition of experimentally obtained peaks into components. A Lorentz function was used, which made possible to determine the position of the component peaks and their half-width. As can be seen from Fig. 9, the spectra from the films mainly show four intense peaks at the wavenumbers (527–539) cm^{-1} , (546–577) cm^{-1} , (631–641) cm^{-1} and (671–674) cm^{-1} .

The results correlate well with the data given in the experimental works [45,53] and theoretical calculations [54]. According to [45], in the spectra of massive zinc stannate in the range (300–800) cm^{-1} , five Raman active modes are usually observed at the wavenumbers of 381, 467, 527, 556 and 667 cm^{-1} . They are usually associated with $F_{2g}(1)$, E_g , $F_{2g}(2)$, $F_{2g}(3)$, and A_{1g} symmetries, respectively. The peak with the highest intensity at 667 cm^{-1} is due to the symmetric stretching of the Zn-O bonds in the ZnO_4 tetrahedra of Zn_2SnO_4 compound with the inverse spinel structure (so-called tetrahedral breathing mode [55]). The other four phonon modes at lower frequencies are conditioned vibrations of the metal ion participating in the B-coordination of oxygen ions, that is, they correspond to symmetric and antisymmetric displacements of oxygen atoms in Me-O bonds in MeO_6 octahedra (where Me is Zn or Sn) [56]. Two Raman modes with close shift wavenumbers at 527 cm^{-1} and 556 cm^{-1} are typical for Zn_2SnO_4 with an inverse spinel structure

Fig. 7. TEM images of Zn₂SnO₄ from crushed film material annealed at temperatures, T_a , °C: 250 (a); 300 (b); 350 (c); 400 (d); 450 (e) and 500 (f). The inset is SAED pattern with reflections from different planes.

and created by vibrations of Sn and Zn cations in the same (octahedral) nodes.

In the Raman spectrum of nanocrystalline stannate, the authors of references [24,45,54] observed an additional peak at a wavenumber of 626 cm⁻¹. In addition, the spectrum of the nanomaterial differed significantly from the spectrum of the bulk in terms of the relative

intensity and width of the obtained peaks. At the same time, the positions of the peaks with other wavenumbers in the spectrum of nanostructured Zn₂SnO₄ coincided with the positions characteristic of the massive material. The authors of [45] associate the newly formed peak with Raman-active vibrations of Sn-O bonds in SnO₄ tetrahedra (having A_{1g} symmetry, A_{1g} (nano)), created by the redistribution of a part of Sn

Fig. 8. Dependence of the pole density P_i on the angle ϕ between the texture axis and the normal to the reflecting plane for Zn_2SnO_4 films at T_a , °C: 350 (1), 400 (30 min) (2), 400 (60 min) (3), 450 (4), 500 (5) °C. In the inset: Dependence of the orientation factor f on the annealing temperature of the films T_a .

ions from position [B] to position (A). As a result, the spinel lattice can change its symmetry and exhibit a greater number of active vibrational modes in Raman spectra.

That is, the observation of this mode indicates a violation of the order of filling positions [B] and (A) in the spinel structure with Zn and Sn cations. Such a change in the cation order in the spinel phase is usually caused by high temperature, pressure, irradiation of the material with high-energy ions or neutrons, and reduction of the particle size to the nanometer range, as in our case [57,58]. That is, on the spectra we obtained from the films, only the modes characteristic of the Zn_2SnO_4 compound with the inverse spinel structure in the nanocrystalline state are observed, which confirms the data of X-ray structural analyses and SEM. In the studied samples, there were also no peaks from the

crystalline ZnSnO_3 compound at wavenumbers of 298 cm^{-1} , 370 cm^{-1} , and 607 cm^{-1} [59], although, in NPs synthesized during 32 h, this phase was detected by the method of high-resolution TEM. Thus, no secondary phases were detected in the films by Raman spectroscopy.

In our case, the positions of the A_{1g} (nano) and A_{1g} peaks shifted with increasing annealing temperature towards smaller wavenumbers values ($641 \rightarrow 631\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $674 \rightarrow 671\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively) which is characteristic of the nanocrystalline material studied in [45]. The dependence of the wavenumbers shift of the $F_{2g}(2)$, $F_{2g}(3)$ peaks on T_a was more complex. Up to a temperature of 400 °C , the shift occurred in the direction of a decrease in the wavenumbers of these modes ($539 \rightarrow 527\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $577 \rightarrow 546\text{ cm}^{-1}$), however, with a further increase in T_a , the reverse process occurred ($527 \rightarrow 532\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $546 \rightarrow 566\text{ cm}^{-1}$). This may be due to the presence of microdeformations in the films. The half-width of the A_{1g} and $F_{2g}(2)$ peaks was minimal for the films annealed at 300 °C , and slightly increased with increasing T_a . The half-width of the peaks corresponding to the A_{1g} (nano) and $F_{2g}(3)$ modes decreased up to the annealing temperature of 400 °C and then began to increase. Since the half-width is determined by the structural quality of the films, thin layers annealed at temperatures of $400\text{--}450\text{ °C}$ should be considered the most structurally perfect.

Fig. 10 (a, c) shows the normalized spectral dependencies of the transmission coefficients $T(\lambda)$ of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs and films. A small jump in the spectra at 340 nm ($\sim 3.65\text{ eV}$) is caused by a change in the radiation source during the measurement.

The calculated absorption spectra of the samples are presented in **Fig. 10** (b, d). It is known that the optical absorption of a semiconductor material is characterized by the appearance of a steep absorption edge caused by optical transitions between the valence band and the conduction band [60]. In the case of NPs, the absorption spectra showed a gentler shape. The behavior of the absorption curve in the region of high energies ($< 4.0\text{--}4.5\text{ eV}$) in the case of NPs is associated with insufficient accuracy of the experimental set up, which at very low values of the transmittance coefficient cannot smoothly transition between different measurement points. Consequently, when converting the absorption spectra, it displays sharp declines and ups and downs of the curve. In the case of films, maxima and minima associated with light interference in films were observed in this region. It was found that NPs

Fig. 9. Raman spectra of Zn_2SnO_4 films annealed at different annealing temperatures (a) and deconvoluted peak into components for a film annealed at $T_a = 400\text{ °C}$ (30 min) (b).

Fig. 10. Normalized transmittance (a, c) and absorbance (b, d) spectra of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs (a, b) and films (c, d).

synthesized for 32 h had the highest absorption coefficient, and the lowest in (16–20) h. In the case of films, layers annealed at a temperature of 450 °C had the highest α , and the lowest α was found at (250–300) °C.

In many studies, the method of determining the width of the band gap of semiconductor materials by approximating the long-wave edge of the absorption is widely used [60,61]. A similar approximation was carried out in this work for the investigated NPs and oxide compound films by using the Tauc Eq. (4). The results of the performed

approximation calculated by Eq. (4) are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 11. It can be seen from Table 1 that with the increase in the time of synthesis of NPs, E_g of the material decreases from 4.02 eV to 3.85 eV. This value is larger than that obtained for a single crystal material ($E_g = (3.60\text{--}3.70)$ eV) [62], while for NPs with a diameter of 23 nm, $E_g = 3.25$ eV was observed [63].

This behavior of E_g , by analogy with work [62], may be related to quantum size effects. In our case, a dispersion of the values of the sizes of the particles synthesized during a given time was observed, however,

Fig. 11. $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs $h\nu$ curves of Zn_2SnO_4 NPs synthesized for different times (a) and films annealed at different temperatures (b).

with an increase in t_g , the average size of the particles still increased and, correspondingly, E_g of the compound decreased. It should be noted that the dependence of $(ah\nu)^2 - h\nu$ on NPs for the synthesized time $t_g = 32$ h revealed two linear sections whose approximation gave energy values equal to 2.56 eV and 3.85 eV. The smaller E_g possibly corresponds to some compound that was not detected by other methods, but it is not zinc metastannate (ZnSnO_3), $E_g = (3.60\text{--}3.85)$ eV [64] or transitions related with energy levels at the forbidden band, that could act as recombination centers in the Zn_2SnO_4 compound.

A change in the E_g of the material was also observed for deposited films. At the same time, with an increase in the annealing temperature T_a from 250 °C to 450 °C, E_g decreased almost linearly from 4.04 eV to 3.63 eV. An increase in annealing time from 30 min to 60 min also led to a similar increase in E_g from 3.75 eV to 3.78 eV. These results agree with the data obtained earlier in the work [65] for zinc orthostannate films where the E_g varied from 3.25 eV to 4.10 eV. The highest $E_g = (3.9\text{--}4.1)$ eV value was observed for films deposited by magnetron sputtering and annealed at a temperature of 750 °C [66,67]. As was shown earlier, both with increasing synthesis time and with increasing annealing temperature, the grain size increases. It is known [68] that the optical band gap depends on the grain size. The size of the optical band gap will decrease with increasing thickness and grain size of thin films.

In the case of films, an increase in the E_g of the material above the values characteristic of a single-crystal material is usually associated not only with the quantum dimensional effect but also with the Burstein-Moss effect [69]. It is a consequence of the Pauli principle: optical quantum transitions are possible only if the state to which the electron transitions are not occupied by other electrons. As the concentration of the doping impurity increases, the Fermi level of the semiconductor moves toward the conduction band. As a result, for degenerate n -type semiconductors, the conduction band will be filled with electrons, and higher energy is required for an electronic transition. In the work [70], where single-phase Zn_2SnO_4 films the different carrier concentrations were obtained by magnetron sputtering, for layers with the highest carrier concentration ($n = 3.33 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), the optical band gap of the material reached a value of 3.89 eV. A similar increase in the E_g from 3.21 eV to 3.87 eV was observed by the authors of reference [46] for films obtained by the spray pyrolysis method at $T_s = 400$ °C and annealed at $T_a = 800$ °C. A drop in the surface sheet resistance from 8100 Ohm/square to 2400 Ohm/square was also observed for these films. Thus, it can be stated that the film annealed at 450 °C, apparently, has the lowest concentration of charge carriers, and at 250 °C - the highest. By changing the annealing temperature and time, it is possible to control not only the optical characteristics of the films, but also the concentration of carriers and, accordingly, the conductivity of Zn_2SnO_4 films.

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that not only the annealing temperature but also the synthesis time and the size of the NPs affect the value of the material's band gap as well as electrical properties. Therefore, the control of these parameters is very important for obtaining materials with the necessary characteristics for their application in electronic devices.

Conclusions

Zinc orthostannate NPs with single-phase structure and controlled chemical composition have been synthesized by eco-friendly hydrothermal method. Afterwards, nanoink was formed based on synthesized NPs grown during $t_g = 28$ h. The effects of post-growth annealing of films obtained by spraying inks onto glass substrates in Argon on the chemical composition, structural and optical characteristics have been determined. Zn_2SnO_4 films with thicknesses of $d = (4.90\text{--}8.45)$ μm with [220] growth texture and an inverted spinel structure consisting of NPs with an average size of (28–36) nm were obtained. The results of X-ray studies that showed the presence of zinc orthostannate, were confirmed by Raman spectroscopy showing the $F_{2g}(2)$, $F_{2g}(3)$ and A_{1g} modes which

correspond to the Zn_2SnO_4 spinel structure. Determination of the optical band gap of the material showed that with the increase in the synthesis time of the NPs, E_g decreases from 4.02 eV to 3.85 eV due to the size effect. An increase in the annealing temperature leads to a change in the E_g of Zn_2SnO_4 films from 4.04 eV to 3.63 eV, which is associated with the Burstein-Moss effect. As a result of research, it has been shown that by changing the time of synthesis of NPs and post-growth annealing, it is possible to effectively control the structural and optical characteristics of films obtained by spraying nanoinks onto glass substrates.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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